

Implementation of the Policy of the Head of the Education Office in Increasing Understanding of the Islamic Scriptures at State Elementary Schools in South Labuhanbatu Regency, Indonesia

Syafaruddin¹, Mesiono², Aziddin Harahap³

¹UIN North Sumatra, Jln. IAIN No. 1 Sutomo Ujung Medan 20253, Indonesia

²UIN North Sumatra, Jln. IAIN No. 1 Sutomo Ujung Medan 20253, Indonesia

³Labuhanbatu University, Jln. Sisingamangaraja No.126 A KM 3.5 Aek Tapa, Bakaran Batu, Rantau Sel., Labuhan Batu Regency, North Sumatra 21418, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This research aims to analyze several things, namely: 1) analyze the policy procedure of the Head of the Education Office in increasing understanding of the Islamic Scriptures in the State Elementary School of South Labuhanbatu Regency. Then 2) analyze the implementation of the policy of the Head of the Education Office in increasing understanding of the Islamic holy book at the State Elementary School of South Labuhanbatu Regency. Furthermore, 3) analyzing the performance of the Head of the Education Office in increasing understanding of the Islamic holy book at the State Elementary School of South Labuhanbatu Regency. This research is qualitative. The process of extracting data holistically, either by means of in-depth interviews with a series of questions, observations in the form of observations, and collection of documents with the aim of obtaining correct and valid data. There are 3 (three) findings that became the result of this research, namely: 1) The procedure for formulating the policy of the Head of the Education Office in increasing understanding of the Islamic holy book, which is in accordance with PP. 55 of 2007 and Regional Regulation Number 10 of 2015 concerning Improved Understanding of the Holy Book of Islam in South Labuhanbatu for regional efforts through religious education in order to encourage local governments through religious education to create people who have noble character, have noble character, have basic knowledge and skills religious basis. 2) Implementation of the policy of the Head of the Education Office in increasing understanding of the Islamic holy book at the State Elementary School of South Labuhanbatu Regency starting in May 2018 by coordinating, monitoring and evaluating teachers. Al-Qur'an literacy educators consist of teachers who are graduates of Islamic Religious Education and those who are not from an Islamic education background with a record of being able to provide lessons to students and have a pesantren background with the approval of the Ministry of Religion office of South Labuhanbatu Regency. Teachers who teach must comply with the syllabus provided by the Education Office of South Labuhanbatu Regency. 3) The Performance of the Head of the Education Office in Increasing Understanding of the Islamic Scriptures at the State Elementary School of South Labuhanbatu Regency by controlling the performance of educators in increasing understanding of the holy book and together with the respective school principals to supervise educators in improving the holy book of the Qur'an in South Labuhanbatu. Every month, educators receive an honorarium of Rp. 1,500,000 from the South Labuhanbatu Regency government and are given training every six months and all honorary teachers use the syllabus provided by the South Labuhanbatu Regency Education Office.

KEYWORDS: Policy, Head of Department of Education, Understanding, Scripture and Elementary School.

INTRODUCTION

The main foundation of Islamic Education is the Qur'an. Al-Qur'an is the main source in obtaining guidance and guidelines for life. Therefore, the Qur'an is the main basis in maximizing Islamic education. The Qur'an is very urgent in Islamic education, in fact students must really be able to read, understand and apply the instructions and guidelines in the Qur'an. The initial step that must be taken by educators is that students must be able to read and write the Qur'an properly and correctly so that it can be continued to the next level (Aziz & Nasution, 2020: 152).

South Labuhanbatu Regency is an area that has a motto of Polite, Saying Wisely, Works. The regent as the highest leader in the South Labuhanbatu area proves this motto by making a policy so that it is hoped that this policy can make the area he leads inhabited by people who are obedient to the teachings of their religion. So a policy was issued.

In Government Regulation Number 55 of 2007 Article 4 paragraphs 2 and 3 it is stated that every student in an education unit in all lines, levels, and types of education has the right to receive religious education according to the religion he adheres to and

Implementation of the Policy of the Head of the Education Office in Increasing Understanding of the Islamic Scriptures at State Elementary Schools in South Labuhanbatu Regency, Indonesia

is taught by educators of the same religion. Each educational unit provides a place to hold religious education. The Regent of South Labuhanbatu believes that religious education is one part of the religious life of the people of South Labuhanbatu Regency. The Regent also wishes to create a society that has knowledge and understanding of the scriptures adhered to in accordance with their respective religions and beliefs, forms people who believe and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character and are physically and mentally healthy.

Based on this, studying the Qur'an is something that must be done both in intracurricular and extracurricular learning. This is because reading the Qur'an cannot be separated from learning Islamic Religious Education and extracurricular Islamic Education which is very beneficial for students (Aziz et al. 2020: 122).

A person's ability to read the Qur'an varies greatly, from those who cannot read at all to those who can read properly and correctly and even understand it. No matter small or big, young or old, SMA or MA, SMP or MTs and SD or MI, an MI graduate does not mean he can read better than an SD graduate, an MTs graduate does not mean he can read better than a graduate SMP, an MA graduate does not mean he can read better than a high school graduate.

In terms of the ability to read the Qur'an, someone who reads the Qur'an is still not good or can't at all of course he needs guidance or teaching to read the Qur'an from someone who can read the Qur'an well and right. So with this guidance, can improve the ability to read the Qur'an for the better. Therefore, it is necessary to realize that efforts to learn the Qur'an in schools are very important.

In an effort to improve the ability to read the Qur'an in students, of course, it cannot be separated from the efforts of teachers and madrasas who have a goal for the success of students. Because the ability to read is a skill that is learned on purpose. Not the same as talking. Listening and speaking skills include abilities that are acquired properly; meaning that children learn the function by themselves (Zulkifli, 2003: 53). Learning the Qur'an is not only the task of teachers in madrasas, but also the duty of every believer. Believers who believe in the book of Allah, namely the Qur'an which is the guide of life. So that students can understand and read the Qur'an, then one way is to guide it.

There is no denying that every Muslim wants to know and explore the teachings of his religion which is so broad. To know and explore the teachings of Islam, it must be studied from original sources, namely the Qur'an, Hadith and religious books that explain these two sources. But to know that, of course, the basis that must be possessed is to be able to read the Qur'an. It is impossible for someone who wants to understand the contents of the Qur'an but cannot read the Qur'an. Therefore, being able to read the Qur'an properly and correctly is very important and one of the problems faced by some students is the lack of ability to read the Qur'an properly, or it can be said that it is not fluent.

The existence of student learning difficulties, especially in capturing the lessons conveyed by the teacher can come from internal and external factors. These difficulties must be found a way out, so that the teaching and learning process can run smoothly and be carried out well

Based on a preliminary study conducted by the author at the State Elementary School of South Labuhanbatu Regency, that the quality of Al-Qur'an learning activities can be viewed from two aspects, namely in terms of process and in terms of results. The activity process can be said to be successful if the teacher in the activity process is able to actively involve most of the students. Meanwhile, in terms of results, it can be said to be successful if the lessons given are able to change the learning behavior of students towards better mastery of competencies. In this case the teacher holds additional lessons that are carried out outside of class hours, namely by holding extracurricular activities reading the Qur'an which are held from Monday to Saturday. It is intended that students can further improve their ability to read,

In order to provide religious understanding to Elementary School (SD) students, South Labuhanbatu Regency which is dubbed the polite district to speak wisely through the Regent Wildan Aswan Tanjung, SH, MM issued the South Labuhanbatu Regency Regional Regulation Number 10 of 2015 concerning increasing understanding of religious scriptures Islam Al-Qur'an on Islamic Elementary School Students in South Labuhanbatu Regency.

Based on the Regional Regulation of South Labuhanbatu Regency Number 10 of 2015 concerning increasing understanding of the Islamic holy book which was stipulated in Kotapinang on December 18, 2015 by the South Labuhanbatu Regent Wildan Aswan Tanjung, learning in order to increase understanding of the Islamic holy book serves to meet the needs of the community there will be additional Religious Education, especially Al-Qur'an education, especially for students in public schools. Increased understanding of the holy book of Islam Al-Qur'an is intended to improve the quality of faith and piety of elementary school students who are diverse in Islam. The ability to read the Qur'an is one of the considerations for every Muslim student to enter a higher level of education.

The implementation of policies and the role of the bureaucracy in education requires an educational bureaucracy that is able to adapt to the dynamics of environmental change and understand the needs of the people it serves. Budiman Rusli (2013: viii) explains that a policy without implementation is just a wish list. As written in his book *Public Policy Building Responsive Public Services* "Without policy implementation is a wish list". Bureaucratic performance through accountability must continue to be improved to create excellent service, especially responding to the public interest. Educational institutions need respect and humane

Implementation of the Policy of the Head of the Education Office in Increasing Understanding of the Islamic Scriptures at State Elementary Schools in South Labuhanbatu Regency, Indonesia

treatment rather than being the target of exploitation and purely ethical political interests that negate the main purpose of education itself. The role of the bureaucracy in school institutions ultimately becomes the pinnacle of policy implementation models at units and levels of education. Here it is necessary to reform the management of the unit and level of education. The process of renewal or management innovation becomes a necessity to solve the problems that are being faced. These problems can be in the form of efforts to equalize education, improve quality, increase efficiency and effectiveness of education as well as the relevance of education. Policy implementation requires organizational and individual compliance with applicable government regulations. The process of renewal or management innovation becomes a necessity to solve the problems that are being faced. These problems can be in the form of efforts to equalize education, improve quality, increase the efficiency and effectiveness of education and the relevance of education. Policy implementation requires organizational and individual compliance with applicable government regulations. The process of renewal or management innovation becomes a necessity to solve the problems that are being faced. These problems can be in the form of efforts to equalize education, improve quality, increase the efficiency and effectiveness of education and the relevance of education. Policy implementation requires organizational and individual compliance with applicable government regulations.

METHOD

This research was conducted in South Labuhanbatu as one of the regencies in North Sumatra. In this study, the research setting is scientific, the qualitative design is naturalistic, the researcher does not try to manipulate the research setting, natural events, programs, relationships or interactions that are not forced as a problem building by and for the researcher. In line with the above, Masganti Sitorus (2011: 121-122) explains that qualitative research is often referred to as Naturalistic Inquiry. In natural research, the researcher does not oblige to form certain conceptions or theories in advance about the aspect he is studying, but he can focus his attention on natural events as they are.

Determination of the source of information in this study includes four parameters, namely: context (atmosphere, circumstances or setting), behavior, events and processes. To integrate an understanding of the complexity of social situations as a source of information, below are grouped all available sources of information in the context of the policy of the head of the education office in increasing understanding of the Islamic holy book at the State Elementary School of South Labuhanbatu Regency.

RESULT AND DISCUSS

1. Procedure for Implementing the Policy of the Head of the Education Office in Increasing Understanding of the Islamic Holy Book

Procedure the implementation of the policy of the Head of the Education Office in increasing understanding of the Islamic holy book, which is in accordance with PP No. 55 of 2007 and Regional Regulation Number 10 of 2015 concerning Improved Understanding of the Holy Book of Islam in South Labuhanbatu for regional efforts through religious education in order to encourage local governments through religious education to create people who have noble character, have noble character, have basic knowledge and skills. religious basis.

Observing the findings above that the The inspiration for this policy activity is Government Regulation No. 55 of 2007 where in article 5 paragraph 8 religious education, educational units are allowed to add content to religious education, whether it is by adding hours of lessons, increasing or deepening material rather than religious learning. In addition, in another article, it is stated that in the PP, religious education which is also an activity in the community can be carried out in mosques, mosques, certain places, so these two things inspire us so that we combine activities to increase understanding of the Islamic holy book in public elementary schools in South Labuhanbatu Regency to students by developing in the learning process but outside the curriculum learning process that is what inspired the emergence of Regional Regulation or Regional Regulation Number 10 of 2015 concerning increasing understanding of the Islamic holy book in South Labuhanbatu.

Policy is intelligence, skill, wisdom, a series of concepts and principles that form the basis and basis of plans in carrying out work, leadership and ways of acting by governments, organizations and so on as a statement of ideals, principles or intentions as guidelines for management in achieving goals (Sagala, 2008: 97). The procedure for implementing the policy of the Head of the Education Office in increasing understanding of the Islamic holy book is in accordance with PP.

2. Implementation of the policy of the Head of the Education Office in Increasing Understanding of the Islamic Scriptures at State Elementary Schools in South Labuhanbatu Regency

Pthe implementation of the policy of the Head of the Education Office in increasing understanding of the Islamic holy book at the State Elementary School of South Labuhanbatu Regency starting in May 2018 by coordinating, monitoring and evaluating teachers. Al-Qur'an literacy educators consist of teachers who are Muslim graduates and those who are not from an Islamic educational background with a record of being able to provide lessons to students and have a pesantren background with approval

Implementation of the Policy of the Head of the Education Office in Increasing Understanding of the Islamic Scriptures at State Elementary Schools in South Labuhanbatu Regency, Indonesia

from the Ministry of Religion office of South Labuhanbatu Regency. Teachers who teach must comply with the syllabus provided by the Education Office of South Labuhanbatu Regency.

Implementing the policy of the Head of Service towards increasing understanding of the scriptures In accordance with the mandate of Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2015, Implementation of activities In accordance with the mandate of Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2015 it is actually or should the education unit be obliged to carry out activities to improve understanding of the holy book, starting at the early childhood, elementary, and junior high school levels.

Decision making cannot be done like turning the palm of the hand. This is because the decision will in turn have an impact on many aspects. Therefore, to get an accurate and considerate decision, certain stages must be passed so that the possibility of negative impacts from the decision can be minimized.

According to Herbart A. Simon, there are at least three stages taken in decision making, namely: (1) The investigation stage; This stage is done by studying the environment for conditions that require decisions. At this stage the raw data is obtained, processed and tested and used as a guide to find out or recognize the problem. (2) the design stage; at this stage the registration, development, analysis of possible courses of action are carried out and (3) the selection stage; at this stage the activity of selecting the direction of action from all that exists (Asnawir, 2006: 215).

The Head of the South Labuhanbatu Regency Education Office coordinates and evaluates teachers, This activity is given 24 hours a day and night and can be carried out in classes and mosques or prayer rooms. And all schools are almost evenly distributed in all elementary schools in South Labuhanbatu, then the teacher coordinates with the principal where the coordination of the teacher is required to carry out teaching activities for understanding the scriptures, and the teachers give each report to the head of service and this report will be evaluated on a regular basis. periodically.

3. The Performance of the Head of the Education Office in Increasing Understanding of the Islamic Scriptures at State Elementary Schools in South Labuhanbatu Regency

The third finding explains that the performance of the policy of the head of the Education Office in Increasing Understanding of the Islamic Holy Scriptures at the State Elementary School of Labuhanbatu Selatan Regency by controlling the education supervisor on the performance of educators in increasing understanding of the holy book and together with the respective school principals to supervising educators in improving the holy book of the Qur'an in South Labuhanbatu. Every month, educators receive an honorarium of Rp. 1,500,000 from the South Labuhanbatu Regency government and are given training every six months and all honorary teachers use the syllabus provided by the South Labuhanbatu Regency Education Office.

The existence of controlling and equalizing perception, As a control of this activity, the supervisor is trying to become a control in the education area at the South Labuhanbatu Regency State Elementary School, the principal participates in controlling activities related to this holy book and then as a continuation of performance improvement activities in understanding the scriptures for us to unite. We train and we share perceptions in achieving targets rather than monitoring the scriptures.

As one of the management functions, supervision or control is the last action taken by managers in an organization. Siagian argues that controlling is a process of observing or monitoring the implementation of organizational activities to ensure that all work being carried out goes according to a predetermined plan (Syafaruddin, 2017: 108). Based on the theory described, it can be judged that the performance of the Head of Service in this program plays a central role and is very serious.

CONCLUSION

From the results of research and discussions that have been carried out as well as a description of the data presented by researchers, it can be concluded as follows:

1. The procedure for implementing the policy of the Head of the Education Office in increasing understanding of the Islamic holy book is in accordance with PP. 55 of 2007 and Regional Regulation Number 10 of 2015 concerning Improved Understanding of the Holy Book of Islam in South Labuhanbatu for regional efforts through religious education in order to encourage local governments through religious education to create people who have noble character, have noble character, have basic knowledge and skills. religious basis.
2. The implementation of the policy of the Head of the Education Office in increasing understanding of the Islamic holy book at the State Elementary School of South Labuhanbatu Regency starting in May 2018 by coordinating, monitoring and evaluating teachers. Al-Qur'an literacy educators consist of teachers who are Muslim graduates and those who are not from an Islamic education background with a record of being able to provide lessons to students and have a pesantren background with the approval of the Ministry of Religion office of South Labuhanbatu Regency. Teachers who teach must comply with the syllabus provided by the Education Office of South Labuhanbatu Regency.
3. The Performance of the Head of the Education Office in Increasing Understanding of the Islamic Scriptures at the State Elementary School in Labuhanbatu Selatan Regency by controlling the performance of educators in increasing understanding of the holy book and together with the principals of each school to supervise educators in improving to the holy book of the

Implementation of the Policy of the Head of the Education Office in Increasing Understanding of the Islamic Scriptures at State Elementary Schools in South Labuhanbatu Regency, Indonesia

Qur'an in South Labuhanbatu. Every month, educators receive an honorarium of Rp. 1,500,000 from the South Labuhanbatu Regency government and are given training every six months and all honorary teachers use the syllabus provided by the South Labuhanbatu Regency Education Office.

REFERENCES

- 1) Aziz, Mursal & Zulkipli Nasution. (2020). *Al-Qur'an Writing Brick Learning Method: Maximizing Islamic Education Through Al-Qur'an*, Medan: Pusdikra MJ.
- 2) Aziz, Mursal. et al. (2020). PAI (Islamic Religious Education) Extracurricular: From Reading the Quran to Writing Calligraphy. Attack: Civil Media.
- 3) Zulkifli. (2003). *Developmental Psychology*, Bandung: PT. Rosdakarya Youth.
- 4) Tanjung, Wildan Aswan. (2015). Regional Regulation of South Labuhanbatu Regency Number 10 of 2015 concerning Increasing Understanding of the Holy Scriptures.
- 5) Rusli, Budiman (2013). *Public Policy Building Responsive Public Services*, Bandung: Hakim Publishing.
- 6) Solichin, Mujianto. (2015). "Implementation of Educational Policy and the Role of the Bureaucracy" in *Religion Journal of Islamic Studies*, Vol. 6 No. 2.
- 7) Sitorus, Masganti. (2011). *Islamic Education Research Methodology*, Medan: IAIN Press Publisher.
- 8) Sagala, Syaiful. (2008). *Contemporary Education Administration*, Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 9) Asnawir. (2006). *Education Management*, Padang, IAIN IB Press.
- 10) Syafaruddin. (2017). *Management of Educational Organizations in Science and Islamic Perspectives*, Medan: Perdana Publishing.